

Financial Democracy in the Fintech Era: Evaluating Transparency, Trust, and Governance amid Rising Digital Frauds

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Abstract: *The rapid growth of fintech industry has redefined financial democracy through maximizing accessibility, visibility, and empowerment to users in the digital economy. Indian Fintech industry is estimated to be at Rs. 12,99,450 crore (US\$ 150 billion) by 2025. The country's mobile-first population, progressive regulatory frameworks, and strong digital infrastructure position it alongside global leaders like the U.S., U.K., Singapore, and China. India has the third largest FinTech ecosystem globally. Nevertheless, this change comes with increasing uneasiness on digital fraud, data abuse, and a lack of good governance that endangers the confidence of citizens. The article evaluates the changing aspect of the financial democracy during the fintech era where the transparency, trust mechanism and regulatory governance. The analysis outlines that enhanced oversight structures, enhancing digital literacy, and risk-sharing approaches between stake holders are necessary. The article suggests that sustainable financial democracy would entail a balance between innovation and sound governance to protect the users and promote fair play in the digital financial system.*

Keywords: *Financial Democracy, Fintech, Digital Financial Fraud, Sustainable Financial Ecosystem.*

Introduction

The world of financial services in India has revolutionized very fast due to fintech industry that has helped the country to speed up its financial democracy. Indian Fintech industry is estimated to be at Rs. 12,99,450 crore (US\$ 150 billion) by 2025. India ranks among the top fintech ecosystems globally, with over 14,500 fintech firms. India has the third largest FinTech ecosystem globally. Digital public infrastructure including Aadhaar, Unified Payments Interface (UPI), Digi Locker and mobile-based banking have greatly increased the availability of financial services to all socio-economic groups. The value of the Aadhaar-enabled services alone has more than 136 crore Aadhaar enrolments and 1470 crore e-KYC transactions, indicating how massive the revolution of digital identity in India has been (Unique Identification Authority of India [UIDAI], 2023). Together with identity infrastructure, UPI has transformed payment behaviours, and billions of monthly digital transactions can lead to financial inclusion. Although this has been achieved, digital financial fraud has increased to jeopardize user confidence and trust in this ecosystem. It has been reported that India witnesses some 6,000 cases of cyber fraud on a daily basis, and around 60 crore in monetary losses every day (Indian Cybercrime Coordination Centre, 2024). Due to the increasing use of fintech, there is also the need to have well-established governance frameworks to safeguard consumers.

Objective of the Study is to assess the impact of rising digital financial frauds on financial democracy and user trust, and to evaluate the effectiveness of governance and regulatory mechanisms in safeguarding digital financial inclusion.

Financial Democracy in the Fintech Era

Financial democracy seeks to guarantee a fair access to the financial services and empower every citizen particularly the marginalized in relation to providing transparent financial systems at affordable and secure rates. This has been greatly

achieved in India, with digital public infrastructure. Aadhaar is the basis of an identity system allotted to promote e-KYC, member authentication, and Direct Benefit Transfers (UIDAI, 2023). DigiLocker, having more than 46 crore users offers storage and verification of digital files. UPI has transformed the digital payment system by facilitating low-cost real-time transaction which is affordable to both the smartphone and feature-phone environment. These factors are the pillars of digital financial inclusion initiative in India.

Fig. 1 Pillars of Financial Democracy

One more significant pillar of financial democracy is digital lending. Digital lending platforms bring credit to other groups of people that have traditionally been locked out of formal banking, including gig workers, micro-entrepreneurs, and low-income families through algorithmic credit scoring, alternative data use and high-speed processing (Mendhekar & Sakkaji, 2022). Increasing reliance on informal moneylenders has been decreased with the shift to anytime, anywhere credit and this has provided more economic opportunities.

As of June 2025, UPI dominates India's digital payments landscape, serving 491 million users and 65 million merchants, and processing Rs. 24.03 lakh crore (US\$ 240 billion) in June alone. With 675 banks onboard, it now accounts for 85% of all digital transactions

The insurtech innovations foster the financial safeguarding, as well, through the digitization of the insurance distribution, claims processing, and customer-engagement. In 2024, the value of the India insurtech market is 10 billion USD which has expected compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 55.4 per cent.

All of these innovations are indicators of the rising level of democratization of the Indian financial ecosystem through user-friendly applications to data-driven product suggestions.

Rising Digital Frauds: Emerging Threats to Financial Democracy

In spite of these developments, the Digital financial fraud is a formidable challenge to the financial democracy. Cybercriminals Stole Rs 23,000 Crore from Indians In 2024 and Bank-related frauds have increased dramatically. The RBI reported a nearly eightfold jump in the first half of FY 2025-26 compared to the same period last year.

The lack of awareness among users, similar looking handles that mimic official payment platforms and the use of fraudulent QR codes to withdraw money in place of depositing them have led to the increased use of UPI and QR-based frauds (PwC, 2022). Hackers apply remote access software, phishing sites, and spoofed support numbers to cheat the users into allowing hackers access to their computers.

Fig. 2 Online financial fraud Ecosystem

Aadhaar-based Payment System (AePS) fraud has emerged as a major weak point especially with rural and low-income consumers. Conmen use silicone or gel to make a duplicate of a fingerprint and then use biometrics information to steal money belonging to beneficiaries (I4C, 2024). Such instances are a huge burden to the welfare recipients, who are dependent on government subsidies accessed by means of Aadhaar linked accounts.

Another form of threat is illegal digital lending applications. These applications are unregulated, and they give small loans with predatory conditions, elevated processing charges, and forceful collection strategies that encompass utilizing and abusing providers of loans access lists and personal databases (I4C, 2024). These predatory practices focus on vulnerable groups, which is against the purpose of financial inclusion.

There has also been proliferation of investment fraud and crypto currency scams. There are task-based job scams, Ponzi schemes, and fake trading sites, materials which abuse users into sending money to mule accounts, and the money is usually laundered through several layers before the trail goes cold (I4C, 2024). Such frauds shake the trust of people on online financial systems.

Digital trust is further undermined by account takeover attacks and malware-based fraud, which cause more significant damage than before. To get an illegal access to the accounts, fraudsters turn to botnets, Android malware, and false customer support numbers (PwC, 2022). The increasingly advanced cybercriminals are putting pressure on consumers and financial institutions to secure virtual assets.

Challenges of Transparency, Trust and Governance

Financial democracy is premised on trust. Nevertheless, as digital fraud has increased, a number of governance issues have been unveiled. Poor level of user digital literacy is ranked among the main issues. Only 38% of households in India are digitally literate. A lot of users share OTPs, install viral software, or follow fraudulent messages without being aware of it (PwC, 2022). Scammers take advantage of this weakness to devise frauds out of human behaviour as opposed to the flaws of the system.

Weaknesses in governance systems between fintech platforms only increase risks. Although the structure of governance required by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is the presence of fraud control, many fintech organizations do not have a proper structure of fraud control, frequent openly sensitive testing or real-time fraud detection (RBI, 2021). The insufficient protection of data and compliance with the requirements is caused by a large number of new entrants being more fo-

cused on speed-to-market than on safety.

Fig. 3 Governance Challenges

Transparency in digital lending is defined as an issue, particularly on an algorithmic decision-making process and non-transparent fee model. With no indication of the process through which creditworthiness is determined and how personal information will be used, it leaves the borrowers uncertain (Mendhekar & Sakkaji, 2022). This kind of obscurity encourages the lack of trust of online financial services.

Another issue of governance is regulatory lag. The fintech sector is changing very rapidly, and the current policy-making systems cannot cope with this pace. Subsequently, there are loopholes in the intermediary responsibility, particularly with the phenomenon of decentralized financial systems with a variety of participants, i.e., banks, fintech applications, payment intermediaries, and third-party service providers.

Enhancing Governance: Measures and Model Practices

India should be able to enhance financial democracy incorporating a dual-layered structure of governance comprising of technology, policy, and popular awareness. Fraud detection systems that are technology-driven are necessary when the presence of anomalies needs to be detected. With artificial intelligence, machine learning, user behavioural analytics, and geo-location tracking, the risks of fraud can be mitigated by identifying the suspicious patterns (EY, 2022). The user authentication can also be enhanced by behavioural biometrics.

Multi-factor authentication (MFA), as well as comprehensive biometric security, is also critical. AePSleasures can be mitigated by more robust biometric encryption, device-based authentication, and multi-layered validation based on Aadhaar (UIDAI, 2023). Accountability and transparency should be taken to a higher level through regulatory mechanisms.

The requirements of the RBI regarding digital lending, reporting fraud, and consumer protection presuppose the importance of increased compliance, periodic evaluations, and increased oversight (RBI, 2021). Empowerment of the users can only happen through digital literacy campaigns. Raising awareness in consumers about phishing, QR-codes scams, remote-access attacks, and good practices related to the digital world can play a significant role in reducing high-risk (PwC, 2022). Such efforts can be reinforced with public-private partnerships.

There should also be coordination between the law enforcement and fintech companies. Websites like the National Cybercrime Reporting Portal (cybercrime.gov.in) and Citizen Financial Cyber Fraud Reporting and Management System (CFCFRMS) have been effectively used to freeze over 2,500 crore money in fraudulent transactions (I4C, 2024). The further development of these

systems and the employment of additional intermediaries will enhance the collective fraud prevention.

Conclusion

The financial democracy pioneered by fintech in India gives enormous prospects of inclusion, efficiency and transparency. The effect of the rapid growth of digital services, however, has at the same time generated the growing environment of financial frauds. It is essential to protect the ecosystem by strengthening the governance mechanisms and transparency, increasing user digital fluency, and the advanced fraud detection technologies. Unless trust and transparency are fostered by a strong governance framework and partnerships, financial democracy can only continue its gain pace.

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References

- EY. (2022). *Competing in the new age of insurance*. EY Global.
- Indian Cybercrime Coordination Centre. (2024). *Recent cybercrime trends in India*. Government of India.
- Mendhekar, P., & Sakkaji, V. (2022). *Digital lending in India: Changing the outlook of loans and credit*. LTI & Pega.
- Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology. (2023). *Digital infrastructure in India*.
- PwC. (2022). *Combating fraud in the era of digital payments*. PwC India.
- Reserve Bank of India. (2021). *Fraud risk management and governance guidelines*. RBI.
- Unique Identification Authority of India. (2023). *Aadhaar authentication and e-KYC statistics*. UIDAI.
- <https://www.ibef.org/industry/banking-india>
- <https://www.ltimindtree.com/middle-east/assets/solutions/Digital-Lending-WP.pdf?pdf=download>
- <https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/digital-fraud-cybercriminals-stole-rs-23-000-crore-from-indians-in-2024-8999288>
- https://dtnbwed.cbwe.gov.in/images/upload/Digital-Literacy_3ZNK.pdf
- <https://kpmg.com/in/en/insights/2025/10/indias-fintech-evolution-from-growth-to-resilience.html>